

The Correspondence Principle and Quantum Time and Spatial Invariance

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A quantum free particle is often described as being a dual particle-wave. We suggested in (1) that the wave feature $\exp(ipx)$ is a consequence of spatial (translational) invariance. The reason it acts as a kind of square root flux/probability is that it is derived from the probability $P(x)dx = dx/L$. In other words, $P(x)$ is x -independent, but there should exist an expression(s) in x which combine to create $P(x)$, i.e. $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, translational invariance is key to the probabilistic form $\exp(ipx)$. We argue here that this invariance leads to notions of the past, present and future (time) for a free particle being included(mixed) in $\exp(ipx)$ because it is a probability. $P(x)=1/L$ maps each dx to a dt and so there is not sense of motion in time. p (momentum) is defined as $mo/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and so one must define $v=dx/dt$ which means one is able to determine the center of mass x of a particle at a certain time. In this picture, there is no probability and the particle moves in time from the past, to the present, to the future. In the case of this particle being localized (bound), it also moves in time. This localization breaks spatial invariance.

As a result, we argue that wave-particle duality involves two different spatial symmetries and involves different views of time. The wave picture $\exp(ipx)$ is tied to spatial (translational) invariance (which means mixed past, present, future time) and this does not disappear in the high energy limit for a quantum bound state. What seems to happen is that the wave features, namely wavelength and tunneling effects, seem to become very small. Nevertheless, the classical bound picture is one which breaks spatial invariance and if the correspondence principle is to hold, it seems that the wave picture must be removed and be replaced with a deterministic particle one. The wave picture does not seem to become the classical one at any energy, we suggest.

We ask: What does this mean for low energy levels? We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(ipx)$ is physical (linked to two-slit interference) and that one cannot pinpoint the particle within a wavelength, but there seems to be a second important feature, namely tunneling. This must exist due to spatial invariance (a completely localized particle within classical turning points violates this invariance). This suggests that a bound state is metastable, not stable like a classical one.

Using $\exp(ipx)$ is equivalent to considering probability and so one may think of an ensemble of localized particles (within the classical turning points) together with bound states for which the particle is tunneling out (breaking the bound state). It is interesting that one must consider the contributions of both in the description of what is called a bound state, although there is a classical analogue to this, it seems, which we will discuss.

Finally, we consider the case of entropy. In the literature (2), $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, and a corresponding Shannon's entropy is calculated which represents spatial entropy. A second one is calculated using $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$. Such calculations, however, do not separate a tunneled situation from a bound one. Even in the ground state one has spatial and momentum probabilities within the classical turning points, but also the possibility of the ground state breaking down (tunneling). In the case of von Neumann entropy, a pure state is said to have 0 entropy, but the quantum approach using $\exp(ipx)$ due to

translational invariance forces one to have a more than a localized bound state. There must be at least the bound state and tunneled state and so it is not clear how such a situation may be said to have 0 entropy, we suggest. An excited bound state is said to be metastable because it may emit a photon (for example) and drop to a lower energy level, but it also is unstable because it may tunnel. The probability for tunneling is very low, but it is nevertheless a key part of the quantum calculation (through boundary conditions).

Particle Wave Duality and Different Spatial and Time Considerations

In Newtonian mechanics, one follows a particle in space and time through $x(t)$. The notion of past, present and future is clear and linked not only to time, but to an exact x position. The particle does not have spatial invariance because it is at an exact point at t . In the case of a bound particle, spatial invariance is broken because the particle is constrained to the bound region (i.e. the space between the classical turning points).

This picture was satisfactory in describing particles until some new experimental results appeared, such as discrete photon energies emitted from atoms and an interference pattern created by electrons (in a two-slit like experiment). These features cannot be explained by the $x(t)$ picture. It seems that a probability picture may be required because one needs uncertainty in x so that a particle may interact with either of two slits.

As a first step, one may ask why probability should appear at all, when $x(t)$ describes a deterministic object. Even though $x(t)$ is deterministic, for a constant v (velocity) one may create a set of dt time weights associated with each dx . In such a case, dt is a constant. One may see immediately that one focuses only on a spatial length, which has invariance because each dx has the same dt value. The particle is not being traced in time, so it seems that there is no past, present, or future. They are mixed together in this probabilistic scenario. Given that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ and that there exists spatial invariance, we argued in (1) that there should be an expression(s) in x which combine to demonstrate explicitly translational invariance. In other words $P(x) = 1/L$ (where L is length) is a consequence of other expressions.

We suggested that these expressions are $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ using ideas of maximization of entropy for x and p . As a result, one has an $\exp(ipx)$ which suggests a region of uncertainty called a wavelength \hbar/p . $\exp(ipx)$ contains no time, but due to the length uncertainty, if a particle meets a 2-slit apparatus for which the slits widths and separations are of the order of \hbar/p , it may interact with one or the other and create an interference pattern. Thus, a new type of measurable interference interaction exists in nature which is not described by Newtonian mechanics. This does not mean that Newtonian mechanics disappears. P (momentum) in $\exp(ipx)$ is still proportional to impulse and the particle still moves with a velocity v needed to define momentum for a given rest mass. Thus, matters seem to be more complicated than the Newtonian classical picture.

Quantum Bound State

It was argued in the above section that $\exp(ipx)$ represents spatial invariance, but a bound state represents spatial localization and contradicts this invariance. Furthermore, it was suggested that p and v still exist for a free particle, even though there is a wavelength \hbar/p .

Given a potential $V(x)$, however, one cannot pinpoint a particle at x with a certain p and v because it may be anywhere within a wavelength. As a result, we have argued in previous notes that conservation is really an average concept.

$\exp(ipx)$ allows for interference as well as the Newtonian impulse concept because $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. It is also based directly on spatial invariance. Thus, using $\exp(ipx)$ to describe interactions in $V(x)$ cannot lead to the particle being constrained within classical turning points because this breaks translational invariance. As a result, one may only describe a metastable system. If the particle is within the classical turning points it is on average bound, but if it is outside these bounds, tunneling is occurring and the bound state breaks. This is completely different from a classical system in which the particle is completely localized within the turning points.

This leads to the question: Why should a bound state, even a quantum one, lead to a picture which includes both the particle within and outside of the turning points? In particular, the wavefunction inside the turning points is influenced by the one outside, so the description of a bound particle does not exist without effects of tunneling which represent the bound state breaking.

We try to give a hand-wavy classical example to describe this situation. If one imagines a single particle bouncing in two dimensions in a box with some holes in the walls, then there is a small probability for the particle to escape. In such a case, the bound state no longer exists, yet, on average, a description of a bound state must include both the case of the particle hitting the wall and bouncing back and the case of it going through a hole. The pressure created on the wall is different in both cases and so to describe the bound state pressure on the wall, both scenarios must be included. We suggest that for similar reasoning, tunneling affects the bound system. The key point, we suggest, is that interactions with $V(x)$ really occur in a translationally invariant manner at least at levels where the wavelength matters, i.e. is of the same length as other lengths in the system (e.g. the distance between turning points).

Issue with Time in the Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state is calculated using $\exp(ipx)$ which is derived using spatial (translational) invariance and probability which describes time weights for each dx . As a result, one cannot follow the particle in time in such a picture (if one examines $\exp(ipx)$). The past, present and future all have the same time weights. Due to translational invariance, tunneling is included, but this would normally be a future event, it seems, because one describes a bound particle (influenced by tunneling) and if tunneling actually occurs, the bound system breaks.

This may not be a problem if one seeks average energy E and spatial density, but it seems to be a problem if one wishes to compare a high energy quantum bound state to a classical one using the correspondence principle. The correspondence principle seems to state that in the very high energy level limit, the quantum bound state matches a classical one. Using $\exp(ipx)$ (which is done in a quantum calculation) means there is translational invariance, a wavelength and tunneling. These features do not disappear in the high energy level limit. What seems to happen is that the wavelength becomes tiny and the tunneling probability almost zero. In such a picture, it seems that there are really no interference effects and that one only has the effect of a

single p within dx (which is large compared to wavelengths). Furthermore, the idea of following the particle from one dx to another and using time to do so becomes feasible.

We note that the quantum kinetic energy $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ yields the classical kinetic energy for any energy value. This might suggest that one requires a probability wave type description at high energy levels, but if the wavelength is essentially negligible and there is virtually no probability to tunnel, one may assign a single p value to each dx such that energy is conserved, which is what is done in Newtonian mechanics. There are no longer any probability considerations, neither due to the wavelength (x uncertainty) nor to tunneling.

As a result, the correspondence principle seems to be equivalent to completely replacing the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ translationally invariant object with the classical Newtonian picture. One approach does not become the other in the high energy limit. It seems that rather, the probabilistic features of the translationally invariant $\exp(ipx)$ essentially disappear and so do not need to be considered.

Entropy

Given that a bound quantum state is metastable due to the spatial invariance associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which do not allow for a completely localized calculation (except in the infinite well potential case), a bound state is really a combination of a localized particle and a particle which has tunneled and broken the bind. We argue that any quantum single particle bound state should be linked to more than just a spatial entropy. Von Neumann entropy suggests that a bound state has 0 entropy, but in the literature (1), both spatial and momentum Shannon's entropies are calculated using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$, where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. These calculations, however, do not distinguish between a bound particle and a particle which has tunneled. It may be that due to a low probability for tunneling, it is essentially ignored and the system seen to be completely bound, but this is an approximation and not fully accurate. It seems that even in the case of a ground state, there is a probability for the particle to be within a bound region and to have tunneled out, hence breaking the bound state.

Even in the case of photons knocking a particle to higher energy levels which then decay by emitting a photon, there is tunneling probability which may break the bound state altogether and this does not seem to be included in entropy calculations. Again, it may be that this is an approximation based on the fact that tunneling probability is very low.

The point is that tunneling effects are not dropped when calculating the bound wavefunction. In fact, the boundary conditions used to solve the Schrodinger equation are directly linked to tunneling.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that particle-wave duality is actually associated with two different treatments of space and time. The particle picture is not associated with spatial invariance and allows localization in space, as in the case of a particle constrained within classical turning points. Furthermore, the particle is followed in time so there is a sense of the past, present and future. This picture, the Newtonian one, sufficed to explain experiments for a long time.

It was found, however, that electrons in atoms changed energy levels in a discrete manner and that electrons could display n-slit interference, phenomena not explained by the particle picture. In the case of n-slit interference, it seems that probability comes into play because there is a chance for the particle to interact with one slit or the other. This suggests the particle is not a point, but is associated with some uncertainty in space, otherwise it would simply go through one slit in an observable way. As a result, it seems one needs to describe this experiment in terms of probability. Probability, however, gives weight to x points. These weights seem to be the amount of time the particle spends in dx. Thus, one maps the x axis to time weights and there is no sense of past present or future. For a free particle, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, i.e. $P(x)$ is a constant. If one argues (as in (1)), that the x-invariant equation must follow from x dependent expressions (and uses maximum entropy in x and p) one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution (with $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$). $\exp(ipx)$ is a consequence of spatial invariance and is also linked with uncertainty in space through a wavelength \hbar/p . Thus, one loses the sense of time and gains a probabilistic type of interaction in space. These ideas are completely different from the classical Newtonian ones.

We suggest that using $\exp(ipx)$ based on linear invariance means that one cannot have a localized state in x, because this would break spatial invariance. As a result, if one uses $\exp(ipx)$ s to explain interactions with a potential $V(x)$, the particle has probability to be within the classical turning points, but also to tunnel out and break the bound state. We suggest that this has consequences on the correspondence principle and entropy. We suggest that even for a ground state, there is a possibility for the state to be bound or broken. We also suggest that one cannot compare the wave picture, even in the high energy limit to the classical one because they represent different treatments of space and time. The wave picture does not distinguish between past, present and future and uses spatial invariance, while the particle one follows the particle in space and time, $x(t)$, and does not impose spatial invariance.

References

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